

Job Satisfaction among Employees in the Government Sector: A case of Ministry of Manpower Inspectors

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Article History: Received on 12st Mar. 2020, Revised on 19th Apr. 2020, Published on 6th July 2020

Abstract

Purpose of the study: The objective of the research is to examine the relationship between the factors – nature of the job, working condition, motivation, career growth and job satisfaction of labour inspectors in the Ministry of manpower in the Sultanate of Oman.

Design/Methodology: The study includes all the inspectors working in the different Human Resources Department branches of the ministry of manpower in Oman. 147 respondents from all the 269 inspectors working in the ministry were selected and the data was collected using a questionnaire. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyse the data. Non-probability sampling technique was used for sample selection based on their job position, knowledge and the effective relationship of the inspectors.

Findings: The result of the research was that there was a statistically significant relationship between the nature of work and job satisfaction; the significant relationship between working conditions and job satisfaction and significant relationship between career growth and job satisfaction. But there was no statistically significant relationship between motivations and job satisfaction.

It was also observed that the Ministry of Manpower fully insures the risks of these jobs. Further, increased attention is being paid to the working condition needs of inspectors, including rental cars and clothing appropriate to the sites, providing incentives, free scholarships and training inside and outside the country to ensure inspectors are satisfied with their work.

Research Implications: This research reinforces the theoretical framework of the importance of job satisfaction between work and inspectors of the Ministry of Manpower through studying the dependent variables that affect the level of job performance to enable inspectors to increase their efficiency and productivity of work.

Practical Implications: Through this research, job satisfaction has been identified with the labour inspectors at the Ministry of Manpower, and the proposals that have been made that serve the Ministry of Manpower in improving the level of job satisfaction through taking study recommendations.

Originality: There was no study was conducted before in the sultanate of Oman in relates to satisfaction of Labour Inspectors.

Keywords: Job satisfaction, Labour Inspectors, Ministry of Manpower, Ministry of Labour, Working Conditions, Motivation, Career Growth.

Introduction

For any business organisations to achieve their goals, they must be very much concerned with human factors. Neglecting human resources, especially in the government sector, leads to a decrease in the performance of the employees. Human resources are among the most important factors driving the most valuable and unique assets of the organization. The success of the management of an organization is to manage human resources – a real, exciting and challenging task since the world is a global village and economies keep constantly changing (Betts, 2020). Managers across the public, private and not-for-profit sectors are increasingly realizing that the employees are the most important assets of their organization and important source as competitive advantage comes from having the best systems in place to attract, motivate and manage the human resources of their organization (Mesch, 2010).

Human resources contribute to the performance and achievement of the goals of any organization, as humans are the main element. Human resources play a major role in economic development, as it is the main wealth of countries, and without them, the other factors like productivity, effectiveness, and client satisfaction will not have any value. Human resources of an organisation are important to create competitive advantage and value in the world market, as essential for development ([Coomber & Barribal, 2007](#)). Any organisation should provide a good working environment, support, and allow workers to develop their potential and motivate them to stay in the organisation. Natural and financial resources, despite their importance, come at a later level compared to human resources. Without the human element, there can be no real development in the foundation, and therefore human development is a necessity and of utmost importance. Therefore, countries put human resources development as a top priority during the planning process, because they know very well that human development is the one that accelerates the comprehensive development process in all fields. Therefore, it becomes necessary to improve job satisfaction. Making employers' satisfaction is not only a strong determinant of increasing individual capability, but it enhances the performance of the entire organisation.

Job satisfaction could be defined as the positive attitude of an employee at the workplace. Job satisfaction will be described as the number of overall positive impact or feelings that people have towards their duties ([Fieldman and Arnold, 1983](#)). The extent of contentedness an employee could experience with the nature of the job and the working environment. Job satisfaction is an important criterion which goes with performance, productivity, and effectiveness related to work and is the most important goal of companies. Job satisfaction is a major factor in any organisation to drive its employees to achieve efficient results. The term job satisfaction expresses the positive feeling felt by the employee in general towards his/her work, due to the fulfilment of his needs and his desires in the work, as it is one of the basic goals that most institutions seek to obtain because of its role in increasing the productivity of workers and motivating them. Motivation is a key factor that leads to job satisfaction. Motivation is the best way to satisfy its employees which results in better performance and outstanding yield which in turn leads to increased productivity in the organisation. Job satisfaction plays a critical role when it comes to the effectiveness and efficiency of the business. It is the employees in the organisation who are considered as the best assets and ladder to success. When an organisation regards its employees and keeps them satisfied it stays in the market for long without any conflict.

Existence of labour law and monitoring the compliance with the labour law and its application by companies will build the labour force stronger. Therefore, labour inspection is one of the core functions of a labour administration system and has been the subject to international standards – set by International Labour Organization (ILO), with references to the Treaty of Versailles and the ILO Constitution. In addition to these constitutional documents, the ILO has adopted numerous instruments over the years dealing with the structure and functioning of the system of labour inspection, either exclusively or as an important element for prevention and labour law compliance ([ILO, 2011](#)).

As per the Ministry of Manpower, Sultanate of Oman, the labour inspection is one of the responsibilities of Manpower, monitoring the implementation of establishments, the provisions of the Labour Law and the regulations and decisions implementing it ([ILO, 2008](#)). Labour inspection is the procedures, controls and preventive measures, the ministry of labour ensures for the effective implementation of the provisions of the labour law and other regulations and decisions related to work and workers. It aims at improving the work environment and establishing cooperation between the parties to work and directing them to the best ways to follow to improve work conditions. It takes legal measures towards violators from employers or workers whenever the need arises.

Ministry of manpower aims at monitoring and follow-up of the implementation of legislation and decisions issued by the organisation for the labour market, verifying the application of private-sector establishments as per the Omani labour law. The concern gets raising awareness, for business owners or workers to familiarise them with the importance of the principles, rights, and foundations legally established by them. The ministry also concerned with the following up of complaints and reports that may affect work relations between workers and employers as its specialists seek to find appropriate solutions to settle disputes ensuring stable labour relations. At the same time, the satisfaction level of inspectors at their work is important which is dependent on various factors. Ministry of manpower exercises the application of the labour law through several departments with different specialities, and labour inspectors perform most of these actions ([ILO, 2008](#)).

The departments in which labour inspectors work are as follows:

- i. Joint inspection team** – specialised in following up non-Omani workers working in the country illegally.
- ii. The Inspection Department** –plays a pivotal role in monitoring the compliance of the labour law by the private sector institutions.
- iii. Occupational Health and Safety Department** –following up the establishments operating in the private sector complying with the regulations for occupational health and safety.
- iv. Labour Dispute Settlement Department** – complaints of the individuals and collective worker cases submitted by businessmen and workers in private sector institutions are pursued.
- v. Labour Services Department** – provides services to workers in private establishments to preserve their rights and to encourage them to increase production and commitment in their work through awareness.
- vi. The Union Syndicates Department** –responsible for the system of forming, operating and registering trade unions in the Sultanate of Oman.

Since we are emphasising the importance of Job satisfaction in Government sectors, human development is the key to satisfy the employees. By laying a strong foundation, Government sectors can be more functional and productive and thus perform a vital role in the development of the Country. The world has realised the critical importance of human resource development and the economic plans aim mainly at diversifying its income sources and assured that this can only be achieved by relying on improving human resources.

The Sultanate was not far from catching up with the world, through attention to human development and investment in human development in a manner commensurate with the capabilities and conditions available to them.

Background of the study

Job satisfaction of Inspectors is very important to the ministry of manpower to keep them contribute more. Recently, inspectors have expressed dissatisfaction over their jobs because of the nature of the jobs, inadequate bonus, and overtime hours, working as an inspector in the Ministry. The salary was not incommensurate with the duties and responsibilities of his position. Some were unable to be released from their duties even after their working hours with no compensation whatsoever. A troubled relationship with the hiring managers also creating dissatisfaction of jobs. Moreover, the inspectors were required to constantly attend the court and they felt this might affect the inspectors' social relations. Further, the allowance provided by the ministry seems to be very low. The inspectors were of less hope about their future career growth. [Azeem](#) (2010) studied the relationship between aspects of the job satisfaction and demographic factors – age and job position, with organizational commitment among inspectors working in the industry sector of the Sultanate of Oman, found the similar things. The decision-makers in the ministry of manpower have the responsibility to provide them with several facilities to reduce dissatisfaction and to ensure whether the inspectors are satisfied or not. The problems faced by the inspectors – nature of the job, working condition, motivation, and career growth, therefore need to be studied to find out the reasons therefor.

Research Questions

The study will undertake the factors that affect the inspector's level of job satisfaction. The study will see if satisfied inspectors are effect by the nature of the job, working condition, motivation, and career growth. Therefore, the research aims to study the factors affecting the inspectors' job satisfaction in the ministry of manpower and finding the relationship between these factors and job satisfaction. The study focuses on finding the answers to the following questions:

1. What is the relationship between the nature of the job to the inspectors of the ministry of manpower and job satisfaction?
2. What is the relationship between working conditions to the inspectors of the ministry of manpower and job satisfaction?
3. What is the relationship between motivation to the inspectors of the ministry of manpower and job satisfaction?
4. What is the relationship between career growth to the inspectors of the ministry of manpower and job satisfaction?

Research Objectives

On the above lines, the objective of the research is to examine the relationship between the factors – nature of the job, working condition, motivation, career growth and job satisfaction of inspectors in the Ministry of manpower.

Review of Literature

Job satisfaction is the favourableness or unfavourableness with which the employees view their work and is the collection of positive or bad feelings with which employees view their job ([Newstrom and Davis](#), 1997). Job satisfaction is a pleasurable or positive emotional status appearing from the assessment of one's job or job experience ([Locke](#), 1970). Greater the employee's job satisfaction, the greater success of the organisation ([Harter, Schmidt, and Hayes](#), 2002).

Job satisfaction is related to incentives based on individual or small groups performance, while organisational commitment is more strongly related to company-level incentives. ([Drago, Estrin, Wooden](#), 1993). Supervision, pay, overall job satisfaction, age, and job tenure were the significant predictors of organisational commitment ([Azeem](#), 2010). The moderate levels of job satisfaction are based on gender and there were differences in the areas of emotional healing, promotion, and the nature of the work - the lower grades ([Al-Mahdy, Al-Harhi, & Salah El-Din](#), 2016). The middle-level management employees in semi-government organisations were primarily driven by an internal locus of control and most of the employees in the sector scored low in the job satisfaction scale ([Hans, Mubeen, & Ghabshi](#), 2013). Workers who report dissatisfaction with their jobs are statistically more likely to quit than those with higher levels of satisfaction. The cross-sectional distribution of job satisfaction responses thus contains information that enables us to predict workers' future behaviour ([Clark, Georgellis & Sanfey](#), 1998). Factors related to productivity, employee motivation, and relationship with colleagues and workers impact job satisfaction ([Troesch and Bauer](#), 2017).

The process of understanding human motivation towards job satisfaction is by identifying three types of basic needs viz. the need for achievement, the need for Affiliation and the need for power ([McClelland](#), 1965). Higher-level needs, such as self-esteem and self-fulfilment, can only be met after lower-level needs are met. ([Maslow, Stephens and Heil](#), 1998). The motivation towards work is a factor that affects an employee's emotional commitment to the organization. ([Saragih, Luturlean, & Hadiyanto](#), 2020). Motivation is vital for organisations to work and without motivation, employees will not put up their best and the businesses performance would be tiny adequate ([Nchorbuno](#), 2011). Motivation relates to the complexity of units that causes a person at work to raise his passion and enthusiasm to use his abilities to perform to accomplish organisational goals ([Badawi et al.](#), 2019; [Ekundayo and Ajanaku](#), 2018). Factors other than finance such as Job security, good working conditions, good working relation with co-workers and employers, assistance in decision making, training motivate workers to perform well ([Florence](#), 2014). Motivation drives a person with a direction needed to engage with the environment in an adaptive, open-ended, and problem-solving sort of an action ([Reeve](#), 2014). General competencies use a mediating influence on the relationship between career success satisfaction and job performance ([Valaei and Nikhashemi](#), 2017).

Career satisfaction as individuals' evaluations of their careers is often seen as one prime indicator of subjective career success ([Abele, Spurk and Volmer](#), 2011; Ng et al., 2005). The job satisfaction was measured as the evaluation of a person's progression toward meeting different career-related goals such as income, advancement, development, and overall career goals ([Hofmans, Dries, and Pepermans](#), 2008). Career satisfaction means satisfaction with the rate of progress and career responsibility is to measure an individual's responsibility towards their jobs, profession, and careers ([Seibert and Kraimer](#), 2001). Largest people aim for job success, which is related to many different forms of career-related behaviour and well-being like proactivity, mentoring, networking, organisational learning climate, self-management, mobility, positive affectivity, and life satisfaction ([Abele, Spurk and Volmer](#), 2011). The factors such as work-recognition, benefits, the nature of the organization, work, etc., that have an impact on employee satisfaction ([Pauceanu, Hisam, & Sanyal](#), 2016). Gender, age, education, and duration of the job mix the level of job satisfaction and factors such as extroversion, openness, harmony and conscience of employees affect job satisfaction positively except for neuroticism negatively ([Al Shuhoomi and Khan](#), 2019).

Working conditions based on various factors (external factors – climate and workplaces, subjective factors – gender, age, fatigue, monotonous, and other organisation related factors – shifts, speed and stress) can influence the level of performance and satisfaction of an employee ([Alegre, Machuca, & Mirabent](#), 2016). The environmental conditions of work such as air-conditioning, lighting, heat humidity, and noise influence the degree of individual acceptance of the work environment, that serious environmental conditions drive to

the satisfaction of individuals with the work environment ([Arafa, Nazel, Ibrahim, and Attia, 2003](#)). Difficult working conditions limit the chances of working effectively in the profession ([Billingsley, Bettini, Mathews, & McLeskey, 2020](#)). Useful for strategies to improve working conditions are necessitated in global supply chains ([Short, Toffel and Hugill, 2019](#)). Increasing satisfaction split into a two-step process which includes first eliminating the hygiene factors, then on the motivators to make people happy at their jobs ([Small, 1971](#)).

Job feedback - the extent to which work activities are taken out provides direct and clear information to the employee concerning how well the job is being done ([Brett, Uhl-Bien, Huang, and Carsten, 2016](#)). Dissatisfaction with routine, has lead Declined output, low absenteeism, works turnover, and work errors, to try finding other jobs (Al-Salem, 2005)

Hypotheses

From the above review of literature, the following hypotheses were derived:

1. There are statistically significant relationships between the nature of the job the inspectors and job satisfaction
2. There are statistically significant relationships between working condition with the inspectors and job satisfaction
3. There are statistically significant relationships between motivation with the inspectors and job satisfaction
4. There are statistically significant relationships between career growths with inspectors' job satisfaction.

Research Methodology

The study includes all the inspectors working in the different Human Resources Department branches of the ministry of manpower in Oman. They were about 269 inspectors 147 respondents from all the 269 inspectors working in the ministry were selected to get information using a questionnaire. It includes job satisfaction as the dependent variable and another four independent variables which focus on working condition, nature of job, motivation and growth career. The study uses the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) for analyzing data. Non-probability sampling technique was used for sample selection based on their job position, knowledge and the effective relationship of the inspectors. The questionnaire consisted of two sections – demographic and job satisfaction, motivation nature of work and working conditions and career growth using the Likert scale.

Findings

Table 1. Demographic information

		Frequency	Per cent
Gender	Male	123	84
	Female	24	16
Age	Less than 25	0	0
	26-35	78	53
	36-45	64	44
	More than 46	5	3
Education	Class 12	4	3
	Diploma	33	22
	Bachelor	95	65
	Masters and above	15	10
Experience	Less than 5 years	8	5
	6-10 years	81	55
	11-15 years	45	31
	More than 16 years	13	9
Position	Inspection	102	69.4
	Legal viewer	14	9.5
	Asst manager / HR section	20	13.6
	Manager and above	11	7.5
Department	Joint inspection team	70	47.6
	Inspection Dept.	52	35.4

	Safety and Health Dept.	5	3.4
	other Dept.	20	13.6
Location	Muscat	65	44.2
	Dhofar	7	4.8
	Albatnah North	19	12.9
	Al batinah South	6	4.1
	Al dhaklia	10	6.8
	Al sharqia North	12	8.2
	Al sharqia South	5	3.4
	Al wusta	3	2.0
	Aldhahirah	12	8.2
	Alburaimi	5	3.4
	Musandam	3	2.0

Source: Survey

Table.2 Test of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
js1	.241	147	.000	.889	147	.000
js2	.196	147	.000	.889	147	.000
js3	.171	147	.000	.886	147	.000
js4	.293	147	.000	.807	147	.000
js5	.184	147	.000	.908	147	.000
js6	.197	147	.000	.891	147	.000
js7	.245	147	.000	.831	147	.000
js8	.145	147	.000	.910	147	.000
js9	.234	147	.000	.884	147	.000
m1	.243	147	.000	.853	147	.000
m2	.277	147	.000	.824	147	.000
m3	.261	147	.000	.821	147	.000
m4	.362	147	.000	.647	147	.000
m5	.244	147	.000	.815	147	.000
m6	.376	147	.000	.626	147	.000
m7	.289	147	.000	.730	147	.000
m8	.324	147	.000	.718	147	.000
m9	.241	147	.000	.801	147	.000
n1	.162	147	.000	.908	147	.000
n2	.186	147	.000	.900	147	.000
n3	.342	147	.000	.744	147	.000
n4	.320	147	.000	.812	147	.000
n5	.255	147	.000	.835	147	.000
n6	.250	147	.000	.796	147	.000
n7	.328	147	.000	.704	147	.000
c1	.173	147	.000	.891	147	.000
c2	.221	147	.000	.899	147	.000
c3	.268	147	.000	.862	147	.000
c4	.148	147	.000	.900	147	.000
c5	.244	147	.000	.883	147	.000
c6	.176	147	.000	.909	147	.000
c7	.222	147	.000	.886	147	.000
c8	.282	147	.000	.833	147	.000
f1	.166	147	.000	.907	147	.000
f2	.190	147	.000	.911	147	.000
f3	.193	147	.000	.897	147	.000

^aLilliefors Significance Correction

Source: Survey

Table.3 Reliability Test coefficients

Alpha coefficient	Job satisfaction
0.945	Stability coefficient all scale (36) items
0.879	The first axis of job satisfaction (9) paragraphs
0.720	The second axis Motivation (9) paragraphs
0.829	The third axis the Nature of job (7) paragraphs
0.911	The fourth axis the Condition of job (8) paragraphs
0.316	The fifth axis Future career (3) paragraphs

Source: survey

The reliability coefficient Cronbach-Alpha estimated to be 0.945, which shows a good level of internal consistency. Table.3 explains the reliability values of all variables were more than 0.6 which indicate that the research questions were strong and reliable. It can be seen that the value of Cronbach Alpha of motivation and working condition were high 0.720, 0.829 and 0.911 while Career growth has the lowest Cronbach Alpha score of 0.316, maybe because of three items for the construct of growth career in the questionnaire.

Table.4 Mean and standard deviation of data of job satisfaction among inspectors in the Ministry of Manpower

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
Job Satisfaction	147	1	5	2.59	1.204
Motivation	147	1	5	2.26	1.188
Nature of job	147	1	5	3.06	1.273
Working Condition	147	1	5	2.50	1.178
Career Growth	147	1	5	3.05	1.281

Source: Survey

Table.4 explains the centrally placed values of all the variables used in this research for the job satisfaction of the inspectors. The mean value for the nature of the job is the highest (3.06). All the other variables and variability among these scores (the standard deviation) is also low showing the less dispersion in data. Motivation has the lowest mean value 2.26 with a standard deviation of 1.188. On the other hand, career growth has the highest standard deviation value of 1.281, with mean 3.05.

Table.5 Correlation Analysis of job satisfaction among inspectors in the Ministry of Manpower

		job satisfaction	Motivation	Nature of job	Growth career	Working condition
job satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	.444**	.549**	.476**	.579**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	147	147	147	147	147
Motivation	Pearson Correlation	.444**	1	.424**	.356**	.553**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	147	147	147	147	147
Nature of job	Pearson Correlation	.549**	.424**	1	.491**	.422**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	147	147	147	147	147
Growth career	Pearson Correlation	.476**	.356**	.491**	1	.367**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	147	147	147	147	147
	Pearson Correlation	.579**	.553**	.422**	.367**	1

Working condition	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	147	147	147	147	147

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey

The correlation coefficient between the motivation and job satisfaction is 0.444, meaning the motivation is causing 44% variation in inspectors' job satisfaction. Its mean if the motivation factor of inspectors among the ministry of manpower increased by 100% the level of satisfaction will rise only 44% that is not very high but is acceptable.

The correlation coefficient between the nature of job and job satisfaction is 0.549, meaning that the nature of the job is causing 55% variation in inspectors' job satisfaction. It means that if the nature of the job factor of inspectors among the ministry of manpower increased by 100% the level of satisfaction will rise only 55% that is not very high but it is at a better level.

The correlation coefficient between Career Growth and Job satisfaction is 0.476, it means the Growth career is affecting 48% variations in the inspectors' job satisfaction. It means that if the Career Growth factor of inspectors among the ministry of manpower increased by 100% the level of satisfaction will increase only 48% that is not very high but is acceptable.

The correlation coefficient between the Working condition and job satisfaction is 0.579, meaning that the Working condition is causing 58% variation in inspectors' job satisfaction. It means that if the Working condition factor of inspectors among the ministry of manpower increased by 100%, the level of satisfaction will raise only 58% that is not so high but at a better level.

Regression Analysis

Table.6 (a) Linear regression of job satisfaction among inspectors in the Ministry of Manpower

Model Summary b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.694 ^a	.482	.467	.883	1.661
^a Predictors: (Constant) motivation, nature of job, working condition and career growth					
^b Dependent Variable: Job satisfaction					

Source: Survey

Table.6 (a) explains multiple correlation coefficient (R) and correlation dependent variable explain (R square). The R-value is 0.694 and R Square is 0.482 very low, so according to the value of R Square value, it is noted that all the independent variables (motivation, nature of job, working condition and career growth) affected the dependent variable (job satisfaction) by 48% . And the standard of Durbin Watson is near to 2, as the result of this test is 1.661.

Table.6 (b) ANOVA^a

	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	103.061	4	25.765	32.331	.000 ^b
	Residual	110.789	142	.780		
	Total	213.850	146			
^a Dependent Variable: job satisfaction						
^b Predictors: (Constant), motivation, nature of job, working condition and career growth						

Sources: Survey

The ANOVA test measures the significance levels of research. Table.6(b) sum of square of regression represents the overall experimental effects (level of satisfaction among the inspectors. the p-value is 0.000, meaning that there is a significant impact between the variables. So we can say that there is strong impact of motivation, nature of the job, working condition and growth career on job satisfaction. Value of F is 32.331, which gives significance with a p-value of .000 (less than the .05 in alpha levels) which means there are

statistically significant differences between the means of different levels of the job satisfaction variable. So it is a good fit for the data.

Table.6 (c) Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	.750	.281		2.665	.009		
	Motivation	.061	.077	.061	.800	.425	.637	1.569
	Nature of job	.265	.070	.281	3.774	.000	.659	1.517
	Working condition	.190	.073	.185	2.582	.011	.714	1.401
	Career Growth	.337	.071	.360	4.730	.000	.631	1.586

a. Dependent Variable: job satisfaction

Sources: Survey

According to the Table.6(c), the significant value of Coefficients regression which measure the relations between dependent and independent variables in the research VIF less than 10 so its standard and the Tolerance more than 0.2, so it is also standard.

There is a statistically significant relationship between the nature of the job of the inspectors and job satisfaction. The Coefficient beta for the independent variable relationship with nature of the job r is 0.070 and the significant value is 0.000 which mean that p-value is less than 0.05. So there is a statistically significant relationship between the nature of the job and job satisfaction ([Alegre, Machuca, & Mirabent, 2016](#)). From this result Hypothesis, 1 is accepted. The researcher believes that the degree of the nature of the work of the inspectors is high due to work challenges, and the inspectors use different skills, capabilities and experiences and allocate their studies according to the nature of their work.

There is a statistically significant relationship between working condition with inspectors and job satisfaction. Coefficient beta for the independent variable relationship with the working condition is 0.185 and the significant value is 0.011 which mean that p-value is less than 0.05. So there is a statistically significant relationship between relationship working condition and job satisfaction. From this result Hypothesis, 2 is accepted. The researcher believes that the degree of working conditions of the inspectors is high due to The capabilities provided by the ministry are good, most tasks are clear, and most inspectors have full knowledge of their work tasks ([Alegre, Machuca, & Mirabent, 2016](#)).

The Coefficient beta for the independent variable motivation is 0.061 and the significant value is 0.425, that means the p-value is more than 0.05. The result indicates that there is no statistically significant relationship between motivation and job satisfaction. This result does not support the hypothesis 3 and therefore hypothesis 3 is rejected.

The researcher believes that the inspectors' motivation level is low due to their dissatisfaction with the inspection allowance, which reflects negatively on their desire to work.

There is a statistically significant relationship between career growth with inspectors' job satisfaction. The coefficient beta for the independent variable career growth is 0.071 and the significant value is 0.000 which mean that p-value is less than 0.05. So there is a statistically significant relationship between the working condition and job satisfaction. This result supported the hypothesis 4 and is accepted.

The researcher believes that the level of career prospects among the inspectors is high due to their satisfaction with work in the inspection profession. This finding is consistent with the researcher's ([Abele, Spurk and Volmer, 2011](#); [Seibert and Kraimer, 2001](#)).

Table.7 Summarised Result

Hypotheses	Results
H1: There is a statistically significant relationship between the nature of the job the inspectors and job satisfaction.	Accept
H2: There is a statistically significant relationship between working condition with the inspectors and job satisfaction.	Accept
H3: There is a statistically significant relationship between motivation with the inspectors and job satisfaction	Reject
H4: There is a statistically significant relationship between career growth with inspectors' job satisfaction.	Accept

Conclusion

The ministry of manpower makes a great effort in caring for its employees and the factors encourage its employees to increase efficiency and job satisfaction. In general, employees whose job satisfaction increases, there will be a positive effect on performance and efficiency. In general, inspectors of the ministry of manpower are happy to work in the existing environment and they are free to carry out their tasks.

Job satisfaction among employees is a goal sort of thing that all decision-makers in all institutions look into. Based on the findings the following suggestions were made: The inspectors in the ministry of manpower are covered by comprehensive insurance for the risk of their jobs. Ministry of manpower inspectors are satisfied with the work conditions and expressed that all facilities are available by the Ministry of Manpower. It is recommended that increasing attention to the needs of working conditions for the inspectors, including rental cars and appropriate clothing for the visited sites. Conditions for entering site require special quality clothing, will enhance the job satisfaction of the inspectors.

Inspectors of the ministry of manpower are not satisfied with the motivation provided by the ministry of manpower, and it was observed that the inspection allowance provided is low compared to the workload provided by the inspectors and also compared to the inspection bonuses with other ministries of the same speciality. Therefore, it is necessary to give overtime to the inspectors after the official working hours as they work long hours. It is confirmed that the ministry gives incentive to the non-material inspectors, which contributes to encouraging enhanced competence and satisfaction among the inspectors.

Ministry of manpower inspectors are satisfied with the professional career growth and it is also confirmed that the ministry provides free scholarships, training courses inside and outside the country to ensure the inspectors' satisfaction.

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